

ECONOMICS OF COAL CARBONISATION.*

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My object in bringing the problem of coal carbonisation before you is to draw your attention to the limited coal deposits of India amounting barely to 1% of the world's total reserves, and the consequent economy necessary to organise a sound national fuel industry. The practice of coal carbonisation is comparatively recent, but the tendency to produce concentrated fuels by carbonising may be traced to the primitive man who started stack-burning of wood, to produce charcoal. A little before 1691 the Rev. Dr. John Clayton, Dean of Kildare, addressed a letter to the Hon'ble Robert Boyle, in which he described an experiment on the production and storage of inflammable gas, distilled from coal. This letter was published in the Royal Society's Transactions in 1781. In 1783 Prof. Jan Pieter Minckelers of Louvain made coal gas and used it the same year for ballooning, and in 1785 and in succeeding years, he used coal gas, purified by lime, for lighting his class room. In 1787, Lord Dundonald made some domestic experiments on lighting by coal gas, but it was not till 1792, exactly a century from the time of John Clayton, that William Murdoch lit up his house and office at Redruth in Cornwall with coal gas. In 1798, he lit up a part of Boulton and Watt's manufactory at Soho in Birmingham, and in 1805 he installed a thousand gas burners at the mills of Messrs Philips and Lee at Salford. It was thus that the attention of the world was drawn to the suitability of coal gas for general heating and lighting purposes. Till then, coal was nothing more than a fossil useful only for burning on domestic gratings and for firing boilers. Soon, metallurgy demanded its share, and coal became an industrial product of considerable value, and the method of its processing began to attract the attention of scientific workers. The practice of coal carbonisation is still in its infancy in India, but in more industrially developed countries it has gone several stages further. Coal is now not only yielding tar and gases on distillation but the coke, under the action of air and steam, is being completely converted into combustible gases, far more suitable and economical for industrial operations than the solid coal itself.

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The history of the later processing of coal is one of how efficiently it could be converted into gaseous and liquid products to adapt them not only to the heat requirements of industrial and domestic operations but also to internal combustion engines. The present position of the heat treatment of coal can be summed up by saying that on the one hand, complete success has been attained in the liquefaction of coal through reaction with hydrogen under pressure and heat, and on the other hand, the same end has been attained through an intermediate stage of complete gasification and the conversion of the gases into liquid fuels. Between these two ranges lie the three types of coal carbonisation that are in vogue today. All these three have for their objective the respective needs of the industries,—coke, gas or tar. The automotive industry has, however, claimed its source of propulsion from liquid fuels mainly, and in countries, where petroleum is insufficient but coal is in plenty, the tendency has been to extract as much liquid fuels from coal as possible, by the simple process of distillation, and when still inadequate, complete liquefaction of coal by complex processes has been attempted. The world consumption of synthetic motor fuels from all processes rose from 2.39 million tons in 1936 to 2.83 million tons in 1937, an increase of 0.44 million of tons. The increase in Germany alone was 0.465 million, so that in the rest of the world, consumption fell mainly owing to the production and use of 0.15 million tons of alcohol in France. The production of benzole has increased steadily, the world output rising from 1.14 million tons in 1936 to 1.27 million tons in 1937. In Great Britain, the production of motor benzole rose to 56 million gallons in 1937, an increase of 10% over the previous year. The output of refined motor spirit from low temperature carbonisation also increased from 0.8 million gallons in 1936 to 1 million gallons in 1937. The activities in this direction in Germany are more noticeable and instructive from the Indian point of view, for both countries lack coal and good coal. Germany showed a large increase in benzole production by 14%, that is, 430,000 tons in 1937 as compared with 378,000 in 1936. The output of oil by the hydrogenation process has also continued to rise. In Great Britain, the Imperial Chemical Industries manufactured 35 million gallons of petrol in 1937 as compared with 33 million gallons in 1936. In the output for 1937, 2 million gallons of aviation spirit are included. The production of synthetic gasolene by hydrogenation process in Germany rose to 850,000 tons in 1937 against 350,000 tons in 1936. Similar operations are noticed in France but on a very much smaller scale and in Japan a hydrogenation plant with an annual capacity of 20,000 tons is reported to be completed, whilst the South Manchurian Railway Co. intends to construct a

plant of 200,000 tons capacity. Italy and Russia are also erecting plants for the hydrogenation of coal, and active researches are in progress on the hydrogenation of tars and oils.

It may be mentioned in this connection that the use of compressed gases as motor fuel is already attracting attention and producer gas generated *in situ* in lorries and tractors has met with a fair amount of use in western countries, specially in Germany, and less in France, England, Italy and Russia. In the U.S.S.R. gas producer marine motors are also stated to have given satisfactory results in service and Japan is proposing to use producer gas for buses in the near future. The recent use of anthracite in portable producers in motor cars, in England, is a further interesting development in the automotive industry. A cwt. of anthracite burnt in a producer is reported to be able to drive a 10 H.P. car over a distance of 100 miles at 50 miles per hour. Assuming 25 miles per gallon of petrol, this quantity of anthracite would be equivalent to 4 gallons of petrol, but the price differential between the two fuels is enormous. The refilling of the producer tank every 100 miles is easy, only the anthracite must be lighted before starting. The replacement of anthracite by soft coke or indeed by hard coke would introduce an economy in our petrol reserve, which, by no means, is large. All these represent a lesson to India which is now on the threshold of industrial development.

In India, of the 23 million tons of coal raised annually, about 3 million tons are used for making hard coke, whilst a little more than a similar quantity is used for domestic purposes where much valuable combustible products are lost. Barring the 3 million tons of coal, processed for metallurgical or foundry coke, the remaining 20 million tons could be utilised for all other purposes in the form of what is technically known as soft coke. By the introduction of a further process, *i.e.*, the Mond gasification of this coke, ammonia equivalent to 80-90 lb. of sulphate could be recovered per ton of coal handled. The low and medium temperature carbonisations are both suitable for producing the soft coke which renders all firings smokeless into the bargain. Besides, the possibility of converting low grade coals into better types of soft coke by blending, is admittedly a great point in favour of low temperature carbonisation, as high grade coal exists in very limited quantities in India. The by-products of low temperature carbonisation are larger quantities of tar (15-18 gallons) than by the high temperature distillation, and smaller outturn of gas (3-4 thousand c. ft.) of higher calorific value, per ton of coal. Both the tar and the gases by low temperature carbonisation have different chemical compositions

from those by the high temperature, but their applicability is not impaired in any way and they are more suitable for specific purposes. Whilst the demand for metallurgical coke puts a restriction to the quantity of coal that could be subjected to high temperature distillation, soft coke could replace coal in all other operations, industrial or domestic. Recent researches by the speaker and his collaborators have given indication that an 'after-coking' of the soft coke produces a substantially hard coke, the use of which in foundry and metallurgical operations is visualised. With a fuller development of this aspect of the question, it would appear that modern high temperature coking may have to be preceded by low temperature carbonisation as a general practice. There are certain obvious difficulties, both technical and theoretical, in the practical carrying out of this combined process, but a plant devised by the speaker and his collaborators, Roy and Ghosh, which will be described later (*vide infra*), has given promising results in this direction. In France, the medium temperature coking process has established itself firmly, and several big plants are in operation. As a matter of fact, the poor anthracite deposit in France has led her to medium temperature carbonisation of coal, which, after preliminary treatment, is eminently suitable for providing a substitute for anthracite. Considering the Indian situation, therefore, it would appear that low temperature carbonisation followed by hard coking has an unlimited scope as compared with merely high temperature coking. It has been contended that low temperature carbonisation is uneconomical and that the cost of plants is prohibitive. Its slow development in England (where the conditions are totally different) has been regarded as proof positive of the uneconomical nature of the process itself. But the fact that the Coalite plants are now carbonising at least half a million tons of coal annually, and that the Government of the U. K. have encouraged the establishment in Wales of a similar plant for treating 180,000 tons of coal annually, leaves no doubt that low temperature carbonisation of coal is no longer in the experimental stage. Besides, a difference in the prices of coal at the mouth of the pit in India and in England must be regarded as a better guarantee for such projects in this country. Then again, there is at present in India a definite market to the tune of one million tons for soft coke which is on the increase. In Germany, where the low temperature distillation of brown coal has been practised for years, several low temperature carbonisation plants for steam coal also exist, whilst many more have been built ready for operation. One might generalise that in countries, where both coal and petroleum are in abundance, the development of coal carbonisation for obtaining liquid fuels would naturally be slow. The United States of America could be cited as an

instance to the point. For India, as already indicated, low temperature carbonisation has a special significance, although against the immediate possibilities of low temperature carbonisation, the absence of suitable markets for the by-products of the industry, has been cited as a ground. The rapid increase in the liquid fuel consumption in this country for automotive and stationary internal combustion purposes, coupled with the low petroleum deposit, is alone a guarantee for the complete utilisation of the liquid products of coal carbonisation. As a matter of fact, petroleum and low temperature liquid fuels in India might be regarded as complementary without bringing unhealthy competition. The low temperature pitch after aeration is suitable for road surfacing, and its use in baking enamel varnish would provide a considerable outlet. The carbolic fraction of the tar, often amounting to 10-20% of the volume has its definite uses, and any excess can under slightly altered technique be used for internal combustion engines, plastic industry, and as disinfectants.

The technique of low temperature carbonisation has developed through many stages of failure. The main features of a workable plant are (i) control of temperature of distillation, (ii) rapid conduction of heat through the mass of coal, (iii) discharge of the coke in the form of pieces of suitable size, with a minimum of breeze, and (iv) the maximum life of the retorts. With the above four criteria in view, attempts have been made again and again in all parts of the world to devise the most suitable plants and processes often differing from one another only in details and not essentially in principle. A brief survey of the situation in 1938 would be as below :

In January, 1938, 736 brown coal carbonisation plants were in actual operation in Germany, distributed as under :

Rolle ovens	588
Carbonisation ovens according to Geissen-Kohlenveredlung	35
Gas Producer with low temperature coke production	38
Internally heated ovens by the Lurgi system	62
Carbonisation ovens of Borsig-Geissen type	5
Internally heated ovens of different designs	8

With regard to low temperature steam coal carbonisation, no less than 15 plants were in operation in 1938, to which must be added a few where the carbonisation is carried out at the medium temperature of about 700°C. The more important processes for low temperature carbonisation are :

A. Externally heated :

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| 1. The Coalite Process in England. | 6. Hinselmann Process. |
| 2. Brennstoff-Technic Process in Germany. | 7. Otto Process. |
| 4. Puening oven in England. | 8. Plate oven of Ab-der-Halden. |
| 3. Krupp-Lurgi Process. | 9. Process of Compagnie Generale
Industrielle Carmaux. |
| 5. Berg & Co's Process. | |

B. Internally gas heated:

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|------------------------------------|--|
| 1. Lurgi Gesellschaft oven. | 4. Coalene-superheated steam
Process. |
| 2. Kollergas-Gesellschaft Process. | 5. Maclaurin Process. |
| 3. Delkeskamp Process. | 6. Kivioli-Lurgi Tunnel oven. |

C. Electrically heated shaft oven (internal).

Of the medium temperature distillation plants, mention may be made of the following :

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| 1. Koppers Process. | 4. Lecocq Process. |
| 2. Otto Process. | 5. Kenup oven. |
| 3. Cellan-Jones oven. | 6. Roser Process. |

A most important development in the low temperature carbonisation process has been the carbonisation of oil-coal mixtures, leading to considerable increase in the tar oil yield. Mention may be made of the rotary oven of Salerni, Brassert-Knowles Process, the Corby Process, Curran-Knowles oven, Biummer Process, Process of the Coal and Allied Industries, Ltd., Process of Messrs The Catalysts' Ltd., National Coke and Oil Co. Ltd., and the Hampton-Ryan Process of America. All these processes were and are still under trial, and their capacities limited to below commercial quantities in some cases.

An application of the carbonisation process for boiler-firing deserves also special mention, as its adoption is a factor of great technical importance. Of the various processes, the name of the Pintsch process easily stands first, but those of Berg, Babcock, Hereng and Stanley Morgan cannot be passed over.

It is beyond the scope of this paper to go into the merits of each of the systems most of which are characterised by one special feature or another. Whilst in general the problem of rapid heat transference to the coal is the main objective, and the refinements relate principally to this, giving rise to movable parts in the carbonising retorts, the ejection of the coke in a form

suitable for domestic use without briquetting has brought round designers off and again to stationary retorts.

Briefly reviewing the characteristics of the different processes, certain generalisations could be formulated. It is obvious that plant design and plant durability will depend upon the method of heating, whilst the nature and the amount of by-products will depend in no small a measure on this factor as well. Internal heating will lead to considerable fuel economy, but also to dilution of the gases, and even partial oxidation of the products of distillation. The structural material for the internally heated retorts can be firebrick, capable of withstanding the usual temperature of carbonisation without much deterioration. Besides, the heating gases being in direct contact with the mass of coal, both uniformity and rapidity of carbonisation can be secured. Thus, the quantity of coal that can be handled is very much more than by the externally heated system of retorts, which must of necessity be of cast iron or cast steel. It would appear, therefore, that internally heated chambers or shafts would provide the most ideal plant, the resulting gases being, however, very dilute and, with easily caking coals, the fire gases cannot uniformly pass out through the mass of coal. The dilute gases necessitate the use of large regenerators or recuperators to attain the proper temperature of firing, and having to deal with large volumes of gas, the plant for condensation of the volatile products is larger and the power for working the burners greater. Modern practice has, therefore, progressed in both the directions of internal and external heating, whether the coke discharged is intermittent or continuous. The externally heated retorts are more compact and simpler, and the volatile oils are definitely more in yield. With a proper choice of the thickness of the coal layer to be distilled and simple but efficient means of stirring, the outturn of coal carbonised can be very considerably increased. It can be shown from theoretical considerations that the time, M , required for carbonisation is related to the thickness, R , of the coal layer which must be penetrated by the heat, by the following equation :—

$$M = K(R + C)^2$$

where C is a small constant depending on the nature of the coal. Working at 713°C with a Pittsburgh seam coal in a $6'28''$ radius retort, the actual time of carbonisation was 335 minutes or approximately $5\frac{1}{2}$ hours (Allison, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1930, 22, 841). The appropriate reduction in the thickness of coal layer will, therefore, achieve faster carbonisation even in stationary charges, and by introducing slow raking or stirring, this speed can

be very much more accelerated. Early in 1937, Sen and Roy (*Proc. Inst. Chem. India*, 1937, 21) designed a technical retort combining the implications of this equation, and a system of external and internal heating at will, increasing the elasticity of operation thereby. It has been possible by this combination to carbonise 8 lbs. of coal per square foot of hot surface per hour, with a heat consumption of 11-12% on the weight of the coal carbonised. As the plant in its simplified form has been tried in two instances with satisfactory results, its working deserves further consideration in view of the oft-repeated drawback in the form of costliness attributed to low temperature carbonisation plants. In designing a technical unit for operation in a country like India at the present state of meagre industrial development, it has to be recognised that capital is shy for new ventures and that the first desiderata of a low temperature carbonisation plant should be its simplicity of operation, cheap construction and introduction of mechanical devices only to an extent that does not substantially reduce the scope for manual labour. The technical plant designed can carbonise 50-60 tons of coal per 24 hours when provided with stirrers, but 36 tons when the coal is stationary and the withdrawal of coke intermittent. The plant consists of an assemblage of several sections of three concentric cast iron cylinders (A, B, and C) having diameters 10', 7' and 3' respectively, and height 3'3" each. These cylinders when they rest on the base plate (D), form three concentric compartments (E, F and G), of which the central (G) and the outermost (E) serve as the coal packing chambers and the annular space (F) in between the cylinders (B and C) is provided with a grating (H) and is used for firing coke to supply the heat. The coal containing compartments (E) and (G) are provided with removable doors at the bottom (I), which can be kept in position or detached, by proper lever arrangements (J). Each cast iron cylinder is provided with a deep circular groove (K) at the top into which another set of three concentric cylinders can fit properly. In this way by placing four such sets of concentric cylinders, one above the other, the proper coal-carbonising retort has been built up with an approximate height of 12' 6". The grooves are all secured gas-tight by fire-resistant cements. The outermost cylinder (A) in each set is provided with a delivery pipe (L) for the escape of the products of distillation. The inner coal chamber (G) is also connected with the outer coal chamber by suitable pipe connections (M₁), so that the products of distillation from the inner coal chamber can enter into the outer and then escape through the delivery pipes (L, L, L, L). These four delivery pipes are separately connected to condensers (M, M, M, M) and the condensed liquids from each of the four condensers collect in separate tanks (I, II, III, IV). The tank (I) which

is connected with the top-most condenser collects oil, mixed with a large quantity of water, whilst the other tanks collect oils with very little water. The reason is obvious, because in the continuous process, while descending from the top, coal loses most of its moisture and consequently the delivery pipes at lower heights discharge volatile products with only the steam of decomposition, and so the tanks which are in connection with these pipes through the condensers collect mainly oils with diminished quantities of water. The gases that escape through the condensers still contain sufficient low-boiling constituents (benzines, benzols, etc.) and, therefore, they are led into a tower (N) provided with a large number of partitions or packed with coke, upon which creosote oil continuously trickles from a reservoir (W) at the top. These fine drops of creosote oil absorb most of the light oils in the gases and ultimately collect in the tank (V) below. This oil is again pumped up to the top and the cycle is repeated. The lighter oils are separated from the creosote oil by simple distillation and the residual oil is again used as an absorbent (*vide* Fig. 1).

There are hoppers (P, P, etc.) at the top through which coal and coke could be charged at intervals. There are also arrangements for internally heating the semi-coke by hot flue gases from the combustion and coal chambers to improve the quality of coke and render it hard, if so desired. As a matter of fact, all the cylinders can be used as coking chambers of the internally heated type.

The wall thickness of the cast iron cylinders is 1" throughout, but the bottom section is thicker. There are thick vertical ribs in different segments, which impart sufficient strength to withstand heavy weights and maintain their shape at high temperatures. There are also angle iron bars fastened to these ribs to give additional strength to the retorts. There are arrangements for hanging sheets of iron plates in the coal-containing chambers (E and G) from the top for facilitating better conduction of heat into the coal layers (not shown in figure). Provision is also made for the introduction of gas, air and steam through the set of three holes (S, S, etc.) at different points of the cylinders. Arrangements for continuous loading and discharging could be adopted by the introduction of helical conveyers as shown in one of the cylinders. Numerous doors at each section permit of short-length poking and consequent easy discharge of coke.

General Considerations in a Technical Unit.

It would be important at this stage to examine the probable cost of a commercial unit of this type of coking plant treating, say, 15 tons per 10 hours, intermittently, or 60 tons per 24 hours of continuous operation.

For the present, an intermittent system will be considered, although there is no inherent difficulty in operating the plant continuously, which would also reduce the fuel and other costs. The 15 ton plant would require 500 c. ft. of fire-brick work to enclose the cylindrical cast iron retorts, the latter roughly weighing 250 maunds (approximately 9 tons). To this must also be added the platforms and hoisting arrangements for the coal to be introduced into cylindrical retort spaces. The hoisting of 15 tons of coal and the other mechanical devices, would not consume more than 3 H. P. H.

	Rs.
500 C. ft. of fire-brick @ Rs. 200 per 100 c. ft	1000
250 Maunds of cast material @ Rs. 8 per md.	2000
Chimney and platform	2000
Constructional charges	1000
Shed (corrugated) over the unit	1000
Cost of fraction of power plant including boiler and air compressor	2000
Cost of a fraction of workshop	1000
Condenser and tar rectifier	5000
	15,000

It is obvious that the last three items have been liberally allowed for to avoid any unforeseen expenses. We can now proceed to formulate a balance sheet for coking coal at Rs. 2 per ton at the pithead.

Cost of coal.

15 Tons of coal at Rs. 2 per ton	Rs. 30
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Cost of carbonising.

	Rs. As. P.
(a) Cost of fuel at 11% of the weight of the coal	3 5 0
(b) 5 Ordinary labourers @ 5½ as. a day	1 11 6
(c) ¼ of a shift Engineer or mechanic	1 0 0
(d) ¼ of a Chemical Engineers's wages	2 0 0
Interest on Rs. 15,000 @ 5%	2 1 0
Depreciation at 10% on Rs. 15,000	4 2 0
Overhead charges including power required	2 0 0
	46 3 6

Total cost 46 3 6

Proceeds.

	Rs.	As.	P.
11'25 Tons of soft coke @ Rs. 2-12 per ton
154 Gallons of distilled tar fractions
Gas (90,000 c. ft.) as proportionate reduction of fuel cost
Pitch 3 cwt. @ Rs. 1-4 per cwt
		<u>31</u>	<u>0 6</u>
		35	15 6
		3	5 0
		3	12 0
		74	0 6

Net profit on Rs. 15,000 is, therefore, $74/0/6 - 46/3/6 = 27/13/0$, which works out at about 66 per cent. Even if the profits were reduced to half, low temperature carbonisation is financially sound.

Two small plants are at present working with retorts of simplified design after the semi-large scale plant described herein. The one supplies gas to the laboratories of the Indian Lac Research Institute, which can treat 5 cwt. of coal per charge of 8 hours (see Fig. 2). This laboratory which was using the Mansfield cracking plant for 10 years, has adopted the small-scale simplified plant for the last 3½ years, working almost every day, and producing gas at a very much cheaper cost. The second plant which approximates more to the design of the semi-large scale plant, was inaugurated by the Bihar Government last year to investigate the possibilities of low temperature carbonisation of Bihar coals. This pilot plant can handle 1 ton of coal per 24 hours of semi-continuous operation. Below are given comparative working sheets for the usual stack-burning method of soft coke production, for the Bihar Government pilot plant and for the tentative plant (yields for which are based on the Namkum plant) described above as a basis for future commercial venture. In Table II are also given figures for actual yields obtained by Messrs The Low Temperature Carbonisation Ltd., London, for samples of Indian coal.

TABLE I.

	Open burning method for 15 tons.	Sen and Roy 15 ton plant per 10 hours.	Bihar Government Pilot plant: (1 ton per 24 hrs.).
Cost of plant :	Nil	Rs. 15,000 (approx.).	Rs. 1,500 (actual).
Analysis of coal used :	Fixed carbon	52.29	52.29
	Volatile matter	26.59	26.59
	Ash	19.62	19.62
	Moisture	1.50	1.50
Yields :	Coke	10 tons	11.25 tons
	Crude tar	nil	195 gals.
	Distilled tar	nil	154 "
	Gas	nil	90,000 c.ft.
	Pitch	nil	3.4 cwt.
			17.25 cwt.
			8.5 gals.
			5.6 "
			5500 c.ft.
			26 lbs.

* Lower and Upper Jharia Colliery, Seam No. 10.

Open burning method for 15 tons.	Sen and Roy 15 ton plant per 10 hours.	Bihar Government Pilot plant (1 ton per 24 hrs.).
Cost sheet : 15 Tons of coal @ Rs. 2 per ton: Rs. 30	Cost of coal Rs. 30 Cost of fuel at 11% of the weight of coal Rs. 3-5	Cost of coal Rs. 2 Cost of fuel at 18 % of the weight of coal Rs. 0-5-9
Labour charges @ -2- per ton of coke	Rs. 1-4-0 5 Coolies @ -5-6 a day Rs. 31-4-0 $\frac{1}{2}$ of Shift Engineer or Mechanic Re. 1-0	4 Coolies @ -5-6 a day Rs. 1-6
Cost of 1 ton of soft coke Rs. 3-2-0	$\frac{1}{2}$ of Chemical Engineer Supervision Rs. 8 Depreciation @ 10 % on Rs. 15,000 Rs. 4-2	Depreciation @ 10 % As. -8-
If the selling price of soft coke at colliery be taken at Rs. 2-12- as stat- ed by the Soft Coke Cess Committee two years ago, evidently the price of coal used by stack burners must have been between Re. 1-3- and 1-10- per ton. Corres- ponding changes in the price of coal under retort- ing conditions would show very much more profits.	Interest on Rs. 15,000 @ 5% per annum Rs. 2-1	Interest @ 5% -4- Overhead charges As. -2-
	Overhead charges includ- ing power Rs. 2 Rs. 46-3-6	Rs. 12-9-9**
Proceeds :	Coke 11.25 tons @ Rs. 2-12 (a) Coke 17.25 cwt. @2-12 per ton Rs. 31 Rs. 2-6 154 Gals. of distilled tar (Distilled tar 5-6 gals fractions (a) Light oil from 8-5 gals. of anhy- 18 gals. @ -6- Rs. 6-12 drous crude tar)	
	(b) Middle oil 47 gals (b) Light oil 0-79 gals. @ -4- Rs. 11-12 @ -6- As. -4-8	
10 Tons coke @ Rs. 2-12 Rs. 27-8	(c) Heavy oil 25 gals. (c) Middle oil 2 gals. @ @ -3-6 Rs. 5-7-6 -4- As. -8- (d) Anthracene oil (d) Heavy oil 2.82 gals. 64 gals. @ -3- Rs. 12 @ -3-6 As. -9-10- (e) Pitch 3 cwts. (e) Gas at the price of @ 1-4-0 Rs. 3-12- fuel used -5-9 (f) Gas at the price of (f) Pitch 26 lbs. -5-0 fuel used Rs. 3-5-0	
	Rs. 74-0-6	Rs. 4-7-3

** Deducting the sale proceeds from Rs 12-9-9, the actual experimental cost per ton of coal carbonised, there is an adverse balance of Rs. 8-2-6. Of this, Rs. 8 are the salary of two research workers on the pilot plant. A technical plant for treating 15 tons of coal per 10 hours would require coolie labour to the tune of Rs. 1-11-6, and supervision charges of Rs 3 only (*vide supra*). In other words, a sum of Rs 4-11-6 divided by 15, *i. e.*, about 5 annas would have been the labour and supervision charges as against the actual figure of Rs. 9-6. Introducing this correction in the actual working sheet of the Bihar Government Pilot Plant, the carbonisation costs including coal would have been Rs. 12-9-9 *minus* Rs. 9-1-0 or Rs. 3-8-9. Or, a profit of Rs. 4-7-3 *minus* Rs. 3-8-9 or Rs. 0-14-6 would accrue per ton of coal handled, which is very much more than could be expected from ordinary stack-burning.

TABLE II.

Analysis of certain Indian coals and yields of products therefrom.

	1.	2.	3.
Fixed carbon	52.29	62.13	61.44
Volatile matter	26.59	28.01	27.64
Ash	19.62	8.48	9.52
Sulphur	0.85	0.60	0.50
Moisture	1.50	1.38	1.40
Coke	16.50 cwt.	16.50 cwt.	16.36 cwt.
Oil	15.28 gals.	16.01 gals.	14.22 gals.
Gas	2495 c. ft. = 18.34 therms.	2688 c. ft. = 18.98 therms.	2627 c. ft. 20.07 therms.
Liquor	11.11 gals.	11.11 gals.	12.63 gals.

The question of fuel economy in the distillation of coal has been discussed from so many points of view in the past and the economy has been effected to such a fine degree that this does not constitute the main problem of low temperature carbonisation to any essential extent. More refinements are possible, say, by the introduction of Bone's flameless combustion. But the real point is the difficult penetration of heat through layers of coal, specially, when the latter is in its plastic condition during the early stage of distillation. This has necessitated the maintenance of comparatively thin layers of coal in the design of most retorts. But the design of coking ovens is to a large extent bound up with the size of coke desired in the end, specially where no subsequent briquetting is contemplated. Up to a width of 9-11" the coking may be considered complete in 5½ hours but if the coal layer is more in thickness, direct or internal heating is unavoidable, if stirring is not resorted to. One has to choose between mechanical stirring and internal heating, according to the size of the coke desired. In the 15-ton unit, 18" annular space for the outer cylinder does not appear to be excessive in view of the fact that both surfaces of this annular are constantly receiving heat. Besides, it is possible to divert a part of the gas from the inner retort to the outer one for heating by its sensible heat or by the heat of combustion with a limited supply of air. The chief feature of the process, however, is the provision of a larger heating surface, as much as one square foot per 8 lbs. of coal per hour as against the usual practice of 15 lbs. per square foot per hour. This would considerably overcome uneven coking, specially, if the annular fuel space is used as a producer and the combustible gases produced here are burnt around or allowed to circulate through the outer cylindrical retort before entering the chimney.

It would further be noticed that no ammonia recovery plant has been taken into consideration, for the simple reason that it would not pay smaller carbonisation plants to recover the much smaller amount of ammonia in the distillation liquor and the gas. Low temperature carbonisation of coal yields 5 to 10 lbs. of ammonium sulphate per ton of coal carbonised. Roy, De and Guha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc. Ind. News Ed.*, 1938, 1, 48) have in their most important investigation on Indian coals studied this point exhaustively in the case of some of the important Bengal coals. Coals with high volatiles yield higher quantity of ammonia, but this is by no means general. From the by-product point of view, coal under 20% volatiles is practically useless, both as regards tar and ammonia yields. The medium temperature carbonisation raises the yield of ammonium sulphate to 20-22 lbs. per ton of coal, but there is a definite fall in the tar yield and change in the characteristics of the tar oils, *e.g.*, in the phenol-neutral oil ratio, and yield of anthracenes.

Thus the specific requirements of the industry should determine the type of carbonisation, and the recovery of by-products would constitute an essential economy. If soft coke, *i.e.*, smokeless fuel is the object, the recovery of ammonia is not so important as the processing of the tar. But if power production by steam turbines is the goal, a combination of low temperature carbonisation with subsequent Mond gasification of the soft coke would appear to be the most rational way of coal treatment. In this combined scheme, both the tar oils as also the highest quantity of ammonia are realised. The background of soft coke as a rational fuel remains as sound as ever, as power producers could make soft coke the starting point for Mond gasification and recover as by-product this extraordinarily high quantity of ammonia. From a critical examination of this process of heating gas production, it could be shown that at the mouth of the pit, electric power could be generated at as low a figure as 0.082 annas or 0.984 pies per unit.

Low temperature carbonisation plants have been quoted at from abroad between Rs. 1500 and 3500 per ton of coal carbonised per day. There is no doubt that by manufacturing the plants in India, a considerable saving on this head could be possible, ensuring thereby larger margin of profit. If the 1.2 million tons of coal that are annually coked to-day to produce about 800,000 tons of soft coke, were distilled in retorts with no more refinement than the collection and fractionation of the tar, we should be saving at least $10 \times 1.2 = 12$ million gallons of liquid fuel per year. Its general adoption as a measure for the rational treatment of coal would for many years place a source of liquid fuels and manure in our hands which we are at present losing through lack of ordinary organisation.

FIG. 1.
Vertical Section of Carbonisation Plant.
(SEN-ROY)

- A—Cast iron cylinder.
- B—Cast iron cylinder.
- C—Cast iron cylinder.
- D—Base plate.
- E—Concrete compartment for packing cop for carbonisation.
- F—Concrete compartment for coke burning for heating.
- G—Concrete compartment for packing and for carbonisation.
- H—Fire bars.
- I—Bottom doors.
- J—Leaves arrangement for opening and closing bottom doors.
- K—Cylinder firing channels.
- L—Delivery pipes.
- M—Condensers.
- N—Condensing pipe between C and A.
- O—Bonanza adapting tower.
- P—Coal delivery hoppers.
- Q—Coal charging hoppers.
- R—Bypass flap.
- S—Gas, air and steam inlet.
- T—Shaft for the helical.
- U—Cleaning device for the outer cylinder.
- V—Packing slit.
- W—Washing oil tank.
- X—Washing oil pump.
- Y—Washing oil delivery.
- Z—Packing door.

[Scale 1"=4' approx.]

Fig. 2 (a).

[Scale 2" = 2.5' approx.]

Fig. 2 (b).

[Scale 2" = 2.5' approx.]

Fig. 2 (c).

[Scale 2" = 2.5' approx.]